

Carbohydrate-hydroxymethylfurfural-amine adhesives: Chemorheological analysis and rheokinetic study

Catherine Thoma^{a,c,*}, Pia Solt-Rindler^a, Wilfried Sailer-Kronlachner^{a,c}, Thomas Rosenau^b,
Antje Potthast^b, Johannes Konnerth^c, Alessandro Pellis^d, Hendrikus W.G. van Herwijnen^a

^a Wood K plus – Competence Center of Wood Composites and Wood Chemistry, Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH, Altenberger Str.69, A-4040, Linz, Austria

^b Institute of Chemistry of Renewable Resources, Department of Chemistry, BOKU-University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences-Vienna, Muthgasse 18, A-1190, Vienna, Austria

^c Institute of Wood Technology and Renewable Materials, Department of Material Science and Process Engineering, BOKU-University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences-Vienna, Konrad-Lorenz Str. 24, A-3430, Tulln, Austria

^d Institute of Environmental Biotechnology, Department of Agrobiotechnology IFA-Tulln, BOKU-University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences-Vienna, Konrad-Lorenz Str. 20, A-3430, Tulln, Austria

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ABSTRACT

Carbohydrates as a component in adhesive formulations have been reported for many years. A rapid cure at moderate temperatures is a remaining challenge in the development of renewable adhesives. Rheology provides insight into all stages of structure formation of a cured polymer. This work analyses the curing of carbohydrate-amine adhesives with and without the addition of 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) as a biomass-derived key reactant in adhesives. Isothermal and non-isothermal rheological measurements were performed to characterize i) the rheology of the prepolymer, ii) the initial stages of curing, iii) the sol-gel transition, and iv) general rheokinetics. The viscosity profile was described by empirical models and showed a deviation from homogeneous curing. Rheokinetic analysis using isoconversional methods and Arrhenius plots showed that HMF reduces the activation energy of the curing reaction. The addition of 5 mol.-% HMF (based on starting fructose content) increases the reactivity by lowering the activation energy of the curing.

1. Introduction

5-Hydroxymethylfurfural is a high-value, bio-derived platform chemical with a broad scope of application. In recent years, the research interest in macromolecules synthesized from HMF-derived monomers has been growing [1]. Previously, we [2] acknowledged that 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (HMF) has a high potential as key reactant in various adhesive systems. The number of developed HMF-containing adhesives is still rather low, even though publications hypothesizing about the formation and involvement of HMF in the crosslinking of carbohydrate-based binders date back to 1926 [3]. As HMF can be produced by acid dehydration of hexoses, mainly fructose, it comes naturally to mind as an additional reactant in carbohydrate-based adhesives.

In the light of rising international political ambitions and social awareness to decrease the use of fossil resources, the utilization of

renewables has been shifting into focus. Recently, Solt et al. [4] evaluated the suitable alternative adhesives for the particleboard industry, which have a potential to meet the requirements for a large-scale processing industry sector. They concluded that still many challenges, e.g. a rapid curing at moderate temperatures (<120 °C), remain to be solved for a successful general implementation of renewable adhesives. The idea to use carbohydrates and amines in the adhesive manufacture is not new. Although several patents were filed [5–7], the material properties and performance have rarely been studied directly. The rapid cure behavior and fast development of mechanical strength are closely linked to the kinetics and mechanism of the curing reaction. To our knowledge, there is a gap in literature on the chemorheological behavior of these carbohydrate-amine adhesives.

Over time, extensive literature has accrued regarding the relation between rheological properties of macromolecules and their material properties such as average molecular weight or polydispersity.

* Corresponding author. Wood K plus – Competence Center of Wood Composites and Wood Chemistry, Kompetenzzentrum Holz GmbH, Altenberger Str.69, A-4040, Linz, Austria.

E-mail addresses: c.thoma@wood-kplus.at, catherine.thoma@boku.ac.at (C. Thoma).

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Literature on studies of rheology during polymerization is less prevalent [8]. This is surprising as there is only a limited number of experimental methods, which have a sufficiently high response at all stages of the curing process needed for the study of kinetics. The formation of high molecular weight molecules and their entanglements can be seen in the variation of rheological properties. Consequently, they also reflect on the kinetics of chemical transformation. Cioffi et al. [8] highlighted the importance of understanding rheological properties and their effects on polymerization processes, especially in view of industrial applications. A complete rheokinetic description of the curing process can only be obtained from a combination of rheological measurements [9]. At the initial stages of the curing, in the flow region before the gel point, the viscosity profile is the most informative. The sol-gel transition point is one of the most important kinetic characteristics. Flory [10] defined the gel point by the appearance of a macromolecule with an infinitely large molecular weight in a reactive system. After the gel point, the most informative rheological parameters are the storage and loss moduli. In terms of rheokinetics, isoconversional methods are a useful tool for studying complex multi-step processes as they are not based on mechanistic assumptions [11]. This enables practitioners to model the polymerization without in-depth knowledge of the curing mechanism and thus to gain further insight in the process itself, e.g. by qualitative analysis of the influence of additives or reactants such as HMF on the polymerization.

This study aims at investigating the curing reaction of carbohydrate-amine adhesives with and without the intentional addition of HMF.

One objective is to characterize the curing reaction via rheological methods and to link them with structural properties of the polymer such as molecular weight of the uncured adhesive or crosslink density of the adhesive network. The chemorheological behavior is studied by dynamic rheology under isothermal and non-isothermal analysis conditions. Rheokinetic analysis is done with isoconversional methods and Arrhenius plots.

Another objective is to clarify whether the addition of HMF has a significant influence on the curing of carbohydrate-amine adhesives and to evaluate the potential of HMF-derived monomers for the application in adhesives for indoor particleboards.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Materials

Fructose powder FF100 (crystalline, purity 99.5%) was supplied by Cargill Deutschland GmbH (Germany). Technical HMF solution (HMF 155 g/L; levulinic acid 8 g/L, water as solvent) was supplied by Fraunhofer IGB (Germany) and stored at 7 °C. Bishexamethylenetriamine BHT (crystalline, high purity), ethylenediamin (purity $\geq 99\%$) and tetraethylenepentamin (technical grade) were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St.Luis (MO), U.S.). Hexamethylenediamine HMDA (purity $\geq 99.5\%$), 2-(2-Aminoethylamino)ethanol (purity $\geq 98\%$), dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and 2-propanol were purchased from Carl Roth GmbH&CO. KG (Karlsruhe, Germany).

2.2. Adhesive synthesis

Fructose and water as solvent were added to a three-neck flask, equipped with a thermo-element and a reflux condenser. The dissolved carbohydrate feedstock was heated to 60 °C. Heating and stirring was done with a hot-plate magnetic stirrer with teflon coating. The first half of the amine was added at 60 °C and left to react for 20 min. The solution was cooled to room temperature. The second portion of the amine was added directly before the analysis. The target solid content after the second addition of amine was 55 wt.-%. The molar ratio between carbohydrate and amine is given in Table 1. In addition, 5% and 50% HMF were added to the HMDA and BHT resins based on fructose content. For the HMF-containing adhesives, the carbohydrate was dissolved in the

Table 1
Studied carbohydrate-(HMF)-amine adhesives.

Adhesive sample name	Molar ratio	Components
Fru-TEP	5.2:1	Fructose, tetraethylenepentamin
Fru-Ethylenediamine	2.6:1	Fructose, ethylenediamine
Fru-AEEA	2.6:1	Fructose, 2-(2-Aminoethylamino)ethanol
Fru-HMDA	2.6:1	Fructose, hexamethylenediamine
Fru-HMF(5%)-HMDA	2.5:0.1:1	Fructose, hydroxymethylfurfural, hexamethylenediamine
Fru-HMF(50%)-HMDA	1.3:1.3:1	Fructose, hydroxymethylfurfural, hexamethylenediamine
Fru-BHT	3.9:1	Fructose, bishexamethylenetriamine
Fru-HMF(5%)-BHT	3.7:0.2:1	Fructose, hydroxymethylfurfural, bishexamethylenetriamine
Fru-HMF(50%)-BHT	1.95:1:95:1	Fructose, hydroxymethylfurfural, bishexamethylenetriamine

HMF solution, the first half of amine was already added at 40 °C and the reaction time was reduced to 12 min. The amount of added water was reduced for the HMF-containing adhesives in order to obtain 55 wt.-% solid content. The second portion of amine was added directly before the analysis. The following adhesives were analyzed in this work:

2.3. Adhesive characterization

2.3.1. Tensile shear strength measurements

The reactivity of the screened adhesive formulations was measured with an automated bonding evaluation system (ABES), as originally patented by Humphrey [12]. The tests were performed according to ASTM-D7998-15 [13]. The uniform, planar and defect-free European beech veneers, 120 × 20 × 0.6 mm, were stored at standardized climate of 20 °C with 65% relative humidity prior to testing. Based on the dry weight 125 g/m² adhesive were applied to the overlapping area of the joint (20 mm × 5 mm). The samples were hot pressed at 120 °C and the press time was varied between 60 s and 600 s. After the pressing, a tensile force was applied and the tensile shear strength of the joint was calculated. For the experiments tested below the relaxation temperature, a cooling phase (60 s) was used directly after hot-pressing, as suggested in the standard.

2.4. Density measurements

The prepolymers were cured at 120 °C for 2 h in an oven at atmospheric pressure. The cured prepolymers were then crushed with a pestle to obtain a homogeneous powder. Typically 20 mg adhesive sample were used. The density was measured using a 10 mL pycnometer. In preliminary experiments, the swelling of cured adhesives was investigated in various solvents. 2-propanol was identified as a non-swelling solvent and thus used as solvent in the density measurements. Each sample was measured three times at 21.7 °C.

2.5. Swelling experiments

The prepolymers were cured at 120 °C for 2 h in an oven at atmospheric pressure. DMSO was used as solvent in the swelling experiments. Approximately 20 mg of each cured adhesive were immersed in 2 mL of DMSO in vials. The closed vials were then put in an oven using a number of test temperatures (21.7 °C, 60 °C, 70 °C, 80 °C, 90 °C, 103 °C). The crosslink density ν_{E_swell} can be calculated from the molecular weight per elastically effective network chain M_c and the polymer density ρ_p . [14].

$$\nu_{E_swell} = \frac{M_c}{\rho_p} \quad (1)$$

$$M_c = \frac{-V_s \rho_p \left(c^{\frac{1}{3}} - \frac{c}{2} \right)}{\ln(1-c) + c + \chi c^2} \quad (2)$$

V_s is the molar volume of the solvent. The polymer-solvent interaction parameter χ is calculated based on the temperature dependence of the polymer concentration at equilibrium swelling c (see Supporting Information, Fig. 3 and Table 2). The polymer concentration at equilibrium c can be determined from the initial sample mass m_0 , the sample mass at equilibrium swelling m_∞ and the density of the solvent ρ_s :

$$c = \frac{m_0}{\rho_p V_\infty} \quad (3)$$

$$V_\infty = \frac{m_0}{\rho_p} + \left(\frac{m_\infty - m_0}{\rho_s} \right) \quad (4)$$

There is an ongoing research concerning the validity and applicability of molecular models describing the elastic and swelling behavior of polymer networks [15]. It is well known, that for non-perfect networks the quantitative values of M_c and ν_{E_swell} have little significance due to the assumptions made in the Flory-Rehner theory, e.g. contributions from polymer chain entanglements are not taken into account [16,17]. Nevertheless, equilibrium swelling is among the most popular methods for determining the crosslink density, this is not least due to the feasible and simple experiments needed. For highly crosslinked samples, swelling experiments give only a qualitative approximation of the real crosslink density [18]. One of the most limiting factors of confidence is the polymer-solvent interaction parameter χ , which is typically assumed as a constant, even though χ shows a dependence on the polymer concentration [19]. A quantitative evaluation is consequently highly uncertain [18], but relative comparisons can still be made.

2.6. Size exclusion chromatography

Adhesive precursor samples were dissolved in DMSO (2 mg/mL) and filtered through cotton prior to addition in a HPLC vial. Gel permeation chromatography was carried out at 30 °C on an Agilent Technologies HPLC System (Agilent Technologies 1260 Infinity) that is connected to a 50 × 80 mm MZ-Gel SDplus LS 10E5Å 10 µm Guard column and a 300 × 8.0 mm MZ-Gel SDplus LS linear 10 µm liquid chromatography column (MZ analysentechnik, Mainz, Germany) using 1 mL/min DMSO as mobile phase. An Agilent Technologies G1362A refractive index detector

Table 2

Molecular weight analysis of the prepolymer and crosslink density of the adhesive network. ρ = adhesive density, M_w = weight-average molecular weight, M_n = number-average molecular weight, PDI = Polydispersity index, M_{c_swell} = molecular weight per elastically effective network chain, ν_{E_swell} = crosslink density.

Adhesive	ρ [g/cm ³]	M_w [kDa]	M_n [kDa]	PDI [-]	M_{c_swell} [g/mol]	ν_{E_swell} [mol/m ³]
Fructose-HMDA	1.316 ± 0.097	209.4	110.0	1.90	742	1.77E+03
Fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA	1.236 ± 0.133	399.2	107.8	3.70	230	5.17E+03
Fructose-HMF(50%)-HMDA	1.303 ± 0.386	274.2	102.1	2.69	4658	2.07E+02
Fructose-BHT	1.024 ± 0.188	259.9	188.2	1.31	787	1.30E+03
Fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT	0.964 ± 0.173	249.3	145.8	1.71	469	2.06E+03
Fructose-HMF(50%)-BHT	1.060 ± 0.353	294.0	118.0	2.49	572	1.85E+03

was used. The molecular weights of the polymers were calculated using dextran standards and the injection volume was 20 µL.

2.7. Rheology measurements

The rheological behavior was studied by dynamic oscillation using the rheometer MCR 302 (Anton Paar GmbH). The measurements were done under ambient air (relative humidity 50%, room temperature 23 °C) using a temperature control unit P-PTD200 (Anton Paar GmbH, Graz, Austria). The disposable, parallel plate diameter was 25.0 mm and the corresponding gap size was 1 mm.

2.8. Isothermal measurements

Rotational flow curves (shear stress, viscosity) were measured over a shear rate range of 0.1–1000 s⁻¹ at 23 °C. The flow curves were used for the rheological characterization of the prepolymers.

Additional isothermal measurements were performed at three different temperatures $T = 85$ °C, 90 °C and 95 °C and the same setup as before. The samples were heated to the set temperature within 20 s. The measurements were done in the linear viscoelastic regime, which was determined by amplitude sweeps.

In general, Chambon and Winter [20,21] proposed that for a self-similar gel network, the two moduli (G' , G'') exhibit a power law dependence on the applied frequency ω :

$$G' \sim G'' \sim \omega^n \text{ with } (0 < n < 1) \quad (5)$$

They [20] also reported a more general method for determining the gel point, which is based on the fact that at a critical extent of reaction the loss factor $\tan(\delta)$ is independent of the frequency.

$$\frac{G'}{G''} = \tan(\delta) = \tan\left(\frac{n\pi}{2}\right) \quad (6)$$

This criterion is a now commonly used for determining the gel point and has been applied for several macromolecular systems [22–26]. For ideal or stoichiometrically balanced networks n equals 0.5 and the critical gel point equals the crossover $G' = G''$. The gel point was determined in multiwave experiments, which have the advantage that a response can be measured simultaneously for multiple frequencies. A fundamental frequency of $\omega_0 = 10$ rad/s and an initial strain of 2% was used for the multiwave experiments, both being well within the linear viscoelastic regime of all tested adhesives. The other applied frequencies were $\omega_1 = 20$ rad/s and $\omega_2 = 30$ rad/s with an amplitude factor of 0.5. The resulting maximum amplitude was 3.14%, which was well within the LVE region. In the gel point, the loss factor $\tan(\delta)$ is independent of frequency. The tested adhesives all showed a frequency independent response also after the gel point. For all tested adhesives, the critical gel point was found at $\tan = 1$ which corresponds to the $G' = G''$ crossover (see Supporting Information, Table 1).

Additionally, the isothermal measurements were used to study the viscosity profile at the initial stages of the curing reaction and for the characterization of the sol-gel transition. The calculation of the activation energy in the sol-gel transition point is based on the Arrhenius equation. The activation energy E_A of the curing reaction can be derived from the slope of an Arrhenius plot, which is a function of $\ln\left(\frac{1}{t_{gel}}\right)$ over $\left(\frac{1}{T}\right)$ with t_{gel} being the time needed to reach the gel point during the isothermal measurements.

2.9. Non-isothermal measurements

Temperature-sweeps were done to analyze the curing reaction of the adhesives in a temperature range between 20 °C and 120 °C with an angular frequency of 10 rad/s and an initial strain of 1%. The viscoelastic properties, such as shear storage modulus (G') and loss modulus

(G''), as well as complex viscosity (η^*) were measured as function of reaction time and temperature. The heating rates for these measurements were 1.0 °C/min, 1.5 °C/min and 2.0 °C/min.

The non-isothermal measurements were used for the rheological characterization of the prepolymers as well as for rheokinetic calculations based on isoconversional methods.

2.10. Isoconversional method

Chemical curing of a materials is frequently studied from temperature-dependent functions of the storage modulus (G') and loss modulus (G'') which are derived from rheological measurements. In general, there are three characteristic temperatures that can be defined. At the beginning of the curing process, at T_i (i = initial), often also referred to as T_{CR} (CR = curing reaction), the storage modulus and loss modulus show a minimum value. A sharp increase of the moduli is observed once the crosslinking and chain growth has started. The crossover point of $G' = G''$ is called sol-gel transition. At the end of the curing process, the moduli reach a plateau value at temperature T_f (f = final). In this study, the Vyazovkins method [27] is used for the calculation of the apparent activation energy. Vyazovkin introduced the variable activation energy as a practical compromise between the actual complexity of solid-state reactions and oversimplifying methods for describing kinetics [28]. The kinetics can accordingly be described by monitoring any parameter, chemical or physical, which changes over time, during the course of the reaction [29]. The degree of curing α is assumed to be directly proportional to the moduli:

$$\alpha_i = \frac{\int_{t_i}^t \left(\frac{dG}{dt} \right) dt}{\int_{t_i}^{t_f} \left(\frac{dG}{dt} \right) dt} \quad (7)$$

where t_i is the time at which the curing initiates and t_f (f = final) is the time at which the process is finished. The denominator of (7) is the total value of the moduli reached during the curing reaction.

The modulus is normalized between 0 and 1 to estimate the degree of curing α , according to (8).

$$\alpha_i = \frac{G_t - G_{ii}}{G_{if} - G_{ii}} \quad (8)$$

There are two basic assumptions of isoconversional methods. The first one states that the rate of a process is a function of temperature and conversion (9)

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = \varphi(T, \alpha) \quad (9)$$

and that (9) is further the product of two functions independent of each other. One function is dependent only on temperature T the other one only on conversion. Vyazovkin [30] stated that most of the time the variation of activation energy results from the fact that the measured rate is a function of the rates of several simultaneously occurring single step reactions. Consequently, the derived apparent activation energy is a function of the individual energy barriers of the simultaneously occurring reactions. Therefore, it varies with temperature and reaction progress. The rate of progress can be formally described as

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = k(T) * f(\alpha) \quad (10)$$

where $k(T)$ is considered the rate and $f(\alpha)$ is the conversion function, which reflects the mechanism of the process [11,31]. Replacing $k(T)$ with the Arrhenius equation leads to (11):

$$\frac{d\alpha}{dt} = A * \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) * f(\alpha) \quad (11)$$

The second assumption is that the activation parameters are obtained

from a set of kinetic runs, such as temperature versus heating rate. According to Vyazovkin's method [27], the apparent activation energy (E_A) at a specific conversion α can be determined by finding the minimum of the equation $\varphi(E_A)$ for a series of experiments (n) performed with different heating rates (β_i, j).

$$\varphi(E_A) = \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j \neq i}^n \frac{I(E_{A,\alpha}, T_{a,i}) \beta_j}{I(E_{A,\alpha}, T_{a,j}) \beta_i} \quad (12)$$

The function $I(E_{A,\alpha}, T_{a,i})$ is defined as (13), the values of $I(E_{A,\alpha}, T_{a,i})$ can be obtained by numerical integration:

$$I(E_{A,\alpha}, T_{a,i}) = \int_0^T \exp\left(-\frac{E}{RT}\right) dT \quad (13)$$

An Excel macro published by Bernandes [32] was used for the calculations of the activation energy based on the isoconversional method.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Screening of fructose-amine adhesive formulations

In an initial screening, different fructose-amine adhesives, varying in chain length and number of functional groups of the amines, were produced and analyzed in tensile shear strength tests and non-isothermal rheological measurements. As can be seen in Fig. 1, the most promising adhesive formulations in terms of tensile shear strength development and curing temperature were fructose-BHT and fructose-HMDA. The S-shaped increase of complex viscosity (Fig. 1, right plot) indicates a curing reaction of these two adhesives that is well within the processing window of wood adhesives (<120 °C).

An objective of this study is to investigate the curing reaction of carbohydrate-amine adhesives with and without the intentional addition of HMF. The industrial production of HMF still faces many challenges, but at laboratory scale high yields of HMF can be produced via acid dehydration of fructose [33]. Consequently, fructose was selected as carbohydrate feedstock. In order to investigate the influence of HMF on the material properties, 5% HMF based on fructose content was added during the synthesis. From an economic point of view, the utilization of low HMF amounts is preferred but to clarify the influence of HMF also adhesives with higher HMF content (50% based on fructose) were investigated.

Fig. 2 shows the tensile shear strength development of fructose-BHT and fructose-HMDA adhesives with and without HMF. The fructose-BHT adhesive has a higher tensile shear strength even though less amine is used in the resin synthesis. Fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA and fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT show an almost identical tensile shear strength development when tested at 120 °C, the same can be seen when higher amounts of HMF are present in those adhesives (Fig. 2, middle and right plot). In general, the tensile shear strength of HMF-containing adhesives is higher than fructose-HMDA but lower than fructose-BHT adhesives.

As observed in Fig. 2, the tensile shear strength development of fructose-BHT is significantly higher than for fructose-HMDA. It can be speculated that this difference is caused by the molecular topology of the amines [34–38]. Without in-depth knowledge of the fructose-amine adhesive structure, all explanations are highly speculative and a topic for further research on structural characterization.

The aim of this paper is to clarify the influence of HMF on carbohydrate-amine adhesives. The addition of HMF, 5 or 50%, to fructose-HMDA increases the tensile shear strength at 120 °C. This trend is not observed in fructose-BHT adhesives. One would expect an increase in tensile shear strength also for the fructose-HMF-BHT adhesives. The absence of the trend (Fig. 2, left plot) shows that the influence of HMF on the material response of fructose-HMF-amine adhesives is higher than the influence of the amine compound itself. This is also underlined by the fact that the tensile shear strength development of fructose-HMF-

Fig. 1. Tensile shear strength development (left) and complex viscosity as function of temperature (right) for different fructose-amine adhesives.

Fig. 2. Tensile shear strength development of fructose-BHT as well as Fructose-HMDA adhesive with and without the addition of HMF, tested after pressing at 120 °C.

Fig. 3. Rheological behavior of fructose-HMDA (left) and fructose-BHT (right) based on non-isothermal measurements in oscillatory mode with an angular frequency of 10 rad/s and an initial strain of 1%, measured at 2 °C/min.

HMDA and fructose-HMF-BHT adhesives is quite similar when tested at 120 °C. In general, comparisons between adhesives with different amine compounds must be done with caution as the structure of the amine compound might have an influence as well. Therefore, the HMF-containing adhesives should be compared to the reference adhesive,

fructose-BHT or fructose-HMDA respectively.

The curing reaction and physico-chemical properties such as characteristic temperatures are studied to bridge the knowledge gap between these bio-based adhesives and their performance.

3.2. Prepolymer and adhesive network characterization

An in-depth structural characterization of the prepolymer and the cured polymer network is an important aspect of future work. Possible reactions of fructose or glucose with amines, as proposed in literature [39], are given in Scheme 1.

From the viewpoint of polymer science, further insights into the curing reaction of carbohydrate-amine adhesives can be gained by analyzing the molecular weight of the sol chains (prepolymer) and the degree of branching in the gel network.

The synthesis time of HMF-containing prepolymers was reduced by 2/5 compared to the fructose-amine adhesives in order to obtain similar molecular weight for the fructose-HMDA and fructose-BHT adhesives with and without HMF (see Table 2). The initial assumption that the secondary amine group of BHT contributes to the curing reaction is reasonable as similar molecular weights were obtained by reducing the amine content in the molar ratio of fructose-BHT adhesives. The characterization of the cured adhesives showed a slight increase in crosslink density when 5% HMF are added in the prepolymer synthesis. This is also reflected in a reduced molecular weight per elastically effective network chain M_c . The addition of higher amounts of HMF (50% based on fructose content) results in an increased M_c and reduced ν_{E_swell} , which is likely caused by the formation of higher molecular weight fractions in the prepolymer synthesis. These results demonstrate two things. First, HMF acts as a key reactant in the prepolymer synthesis by forming reactive compounds. Second, the increase in crosslink density suggests that HMF also has a positive effect on the curing reaction.

3.3. Characteristic temperatures

Non-isothermal, rheological experiments were used to identify the characteristic temperatures of the studied adhesives. The S-shaped response of the storage modulus G' (filled symbols) and loss modulus G'' (empty symbols) is typical for a curing reaction and can be seen in Fig. 3.

Winter and Chambon [20,21] proposed a general method for the gel point determination, which is based on the observation that at a critical extent of conversion the loss factor is independent of frequency. In fact, isothermal multiwave test showed that after a certain extent of conversion the herein studied adhesives show a frequency independent material behavior (see Supporting Information, Figs. 1 and 2). Multi-wave tests confirmed that the critical gel point (sol-gel transition, T_{SG}) occurs at $\tan \delta = 1$, which corresponds to the second crossover point $G' = G''$ in Fig. 3 (left graph).

The onset temperature of a curing reaction (T_{CR}) as well as T_{SG} are important for defining the optimal material processing window. The characteristic temperatures of the studied adhesives are given in Table 3. Recently, it was reported that HMF causes a shift of the curing reaction of adhesives to temperatures higher than suitable for the application in wood materials [2]. This was not observed for the studied fructose-HMF-amine adhesives. The characteristic temperatures of

Table 3

Characteristic temperatures of the studied adhesive measured in oscillatory temperature-sweeps with a heating rate of 2 °C/min, T_{CR} = Onset temperature of curing reaction, T_{SG} = sol-gel transition temperature.

Adhesive	T_{relax}	T_{CR} [°C]	T_{SG} [°C]
Fructose-HMDA	60.3	93.0	96.3
Fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA	–	85.1	92.9
Fructose-HMF(50%)-HMDA	–	86.4	98.9
Fructose-BHT	41.5	87.5	93.0
Fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT	43.7	77.7	87.7
Fructose-HMF(50%)-BHT	–	88.6	93.0

fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA and fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT are significantly lower than the corresponding adhesives without HMF (see Table 3). This positive effect is not as pronounced when higher amounts of HMF (50% based on fructose content) are present.

The curing reaction of fructose-HMDA starts at higher temperatures ($T_{CR} = 93.0$ °C) than fructose-BHT ($T_{CR} = 87.5$ °C), this certainly also attributes to the fast development of tensile strength of the fructose-BHT adhesive (Fig. 2, left plot).

As can be seen in Fig. 3 (left plot), fructose-HMDA shows a crossover $G' = G''$ also below T_{CR} . This characteristic temperature is herein referred to as T_{relax} and is followed by a significant drop in G' . This is an indication of the breakage of non-covalent bonds, e.g. hydrogen bonds, due to enhanced mobility of the polymer chains. In general, relaxations of certain functional groups are another plausible explanation of this solid-to-liquid transition. T_{relax} was completely absent in the 50% HMF-containing adhesives (Table 3). These β - and β' -relaxations were also reported for epoxide resins cured with diamines [37,38,40]. There have been numerous works studying the influence of the molecular topology of amine curing agents on the properties of epoxy resins, recently they focused on aromatic or branched polyamines [34–38]. Even though there is a large number of existing studies, the exact influence of the molecular topology of the amines on the performance of epoxy adhesive remains yet little understood [34]. In this study the relaxations were only observed in BHT-containing adhesives. This indicates that even though HMDA and BHT are both linear amines, the molecular topology of the resulting adhesive is influenced by the number of functional groups and the chain length of the amines. It can be assumed that these relaxations (Table 3) influence the mechanical properties of the carbohydrate-amine adhesive. In order to investigate this further, the tensile shear strength was measured at temperatures below T_{relax} by applying a cooling step to room temperature after hot pressing at 120°, this is also suggested for testing of thermoplastic materials in the standard. Fig. 4 shows that the tensile shear strength of BHT-containing adhesives increases when tested at room temperature.

The values of $T_{test} = 120$ °C in Fig. 4 corresponds to the tensile shear strength of the adhesives in Fig. 2 after pressing for 60s. They were added to highlight any influences caused by the application of a cooling step to $T_{test} < T_{relax}$ before testing. HMDA-based adhesive did not show a

Scheme 1. Proposed reaction between fructose and primary amines.

Fig. 4. Tensile shear strength after pressing for 60 s at 120 °C without cooling ($T_{\text{test}} = 120^{\circ}\text{C}$) and with cooling to $T_{\text{test}} < T_{\text{relax}}$ before testing.

relaxation temperature, but for a comparison they were also cooled for 60s before testing ($T_{\text{test}} < T_{\text{relax}}$). Fig. 4 visualizes that the addition of 5% HMF improves the tensile shear strength of cured fructose-BHT adhesives when tested at $T < T_{\text{relax}}$. One reason for this is that the onset of the curing reaction T_{CR} is shifted to 77.7 °C for fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT adhesives compared to the reference fructose-BHT with 87.5 °C (Table 3).

The reduction of T_{CR} is also observed for fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA adhesives, but the improvement in tensile shear strength cannot be seen after 60s of hot pressing (Fig. 4). Fig. 2 (middle plot) shows that the addition of 5% HMF also improves the tensile shear strength of fructose-HMDA adhesives with $3.65 \pm 0.09 \text{ N/mm}^2$ compared to $3.11 \pm 0.14 \text{ N/mm}^2$ for the reference fructose-HMDA, but significantly longer press times (600s hot pressing at 120 °C, Fig. 2) are needed. The adhesive fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT had the highest tensile shear strength with $4.98 \pm 0.28 \text{ N/mm}^2$ (Fig. 4). Based on Figs. 4 and 2, it can be seen that the addition of HMF clearly has a positive influence on the tensile shear strength of both fructose-BHT and fructose-HMDA adhesives. In case of BHT-containing adhesives, the addition of HMF increased the thermo-plastic behavior of the adhesive, which can be observed in a dramatic increase in tensile shear strength when tested at room temperature. The tensile shear strength of fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT adhesives, hot-pressed at 120 °C and cooled to $T_{\text{test}} < T_{\text{relax}}$, is comparable to phenol-formaldehyde adhesives [41]. Rheokinetic analysis is used to further investigate the influence of HMF on the curing reaction further.

3.4. Rheokinetic analysis

In general, the rheological behavior of a reactive polymer system is governed by two superimposing phenomena [42]. The first one is caused by the increasing mobility of the polymer chains with increasing temperature, which results in decreasing viscosity. The other phenomenon is caused by the growing size of molecules during the curing process and causes an increase in viscosity. At the beginning of a curing process, the initial viscosity, also often referred to as zero time viscosity, and the rate of viscosity change with time can be described by an Arrhenius-type equation. An empirical model [43] that is often used to describe the temperature-time profile of viscosity data is

$$\ln(\eta) = \ln(\eta_0) + Kt \quad (14)$$

where η_0 represents the initial viscosity and K is the viscosity kinetic constant. It is important to note that this simple model (8) does formally not hold for the gel point. The overall fit of the model would be improved when the measured values of the zero shear viscosity are used, but especially at elevated temperatures there is limited amount of time before the curing reaction starts. Consequently, both the initial viscosity and the viscosity kinetic constant were obtained by fitting the model to the experimental data. The complex viscosity profile was used for the rheokinetic analysis. The complex viscosity has the same information as the complex modulus and is consequently frequency-dependent. Isothermal measurements at 10 rad/s were used for the rheokinetic analysis. In general, the studied adhesives do not show a strong frequency-dependency (see Supporting Information, Figs. 1 and 2) and the standard deviation of the degree of conversion for isothermal experiments measured at different frequencies is <1% at the initial stages of curing (Supporting Information, Table 4).

It is important to note that the simple model (14) does formally not hold for the gel point. The viscosity increases drastically at the gel point with $\eta \rightarrow \infty$ even though $t_{\text{gel}} \ll \infty$. Nevertheless, these equations provide

Table 4

Activation energy at the initial stages of curing ($\alpha < 1\%$) and in the gel point for HMDA- and BHT-based adhesives.

Adhesive	Initial stages of curing		Sol-gel transition point		
	E_A [kJ/mol]	E_A [kJ/mol]	t_{gel} (85 °C) [s]	t_{gel} (90 °C) [s]	t_{gel} (95 °C) [s]
Fructose-HMDA	146.75	58.10	721	472	425
Fructose-HMF (5%)-HMDA	141.23	76.72	464	401	230
Fructose-HMF (50%)-HMDA	112.12	85.04	723	461	333
Fructose-BHT	155.37	74.74	607	421	307
Fructose-HMF (5%)-BHT	78.63	64.02	649	470	362
Fructose-HMF (50%)-BHT	61.18	65.49	698	523	384

sufficient accuracy to predict the viscosity of a reactive system and give important information for practical purposes. (13) can also be expressed as:

$$\eta = \eta_0 \cdot e^{k_t} \quad (15)$$

This empirical model was used to describe various adhesive systems such as epoxy [44] or polyfurfuryl alcohol [45] based adhesives or metallo polyurethane curing [46]. As can be seen in Fig. 5 (upper graphs), it is also applicable to fructose-amine adhesives. Using equations (14) and (14), the experimental data of the isothermal measurements was fitted with linear regression as well as with an exponential fit, giving consistent results at 85 °C, 90 °C and 95 °C (Supporting Information, Table 3). The viscosity profile (Fig. 5, upper graphs) can be used to define a flow window for practical purposes. The activation energy at the initial stages of the curing reaction can be calculated from the viscosity profile, more precisely from the Arrhenius plot of the viscosity kinetic constant as function of 1/T (see Fig. 5, lower graphs).

The viscosity does not only vary with temperature and flow conditions, but also with increasing polymerization. The viscosity increase in Fig. 5 (upper left side) is caused by the growing size of polymer molecules during the curing process. As the prepolymers of fructose-HMF (5%)-HMDA had the highest M_w , the curing reaction proceeds much faster. This is very much a key aspect to be considered in future attempts to increase the cure speed of adhesives.

The Arrhenius equation can be used to determine the temperature dependency of the curing reaction in the gel point. The apparent activation energy E_A of the curing reaction is derived from the slope of an Arrhenius plot (Fig. 6).

Interestingly, even though the amount of BHT is reduced in the adhesive system, it is significantly more reactive than fructose-HMDA. As can be seen in Table 4, fructose-HMDA has a lower activation energy ($E_A = 58.10$ kJ/mol) than fructose-BHT ($E_A = 74.74$ kJ/mol). The increased reactivity should lower the gel time and increase tensile shear strength. This is not the case. The gel point of fructose-BHT is reached 114 s earlier than in the fructose-HMDA at 85 °C, and 118 s earlier at 95 °C. Non-isothermal analysis showed that T_{CR} of fructose-HMDA is shifted to higher temperatures ($T_{CR} = 93.0$ °C) compared to fructose-BHT ($T_{CR} = 87.5$ °C). This impacts on the material performance.

As can be seen in Table 4, higher amounts of HMF (50% based on fructose content) prolong the gel point compared to 5% HMF. This might be due to an increased occurrence of side reactions in the prepolymer synthesis, e.g. HMF self-condensation, which also explains the increased E_A of 50% HMF-containing adhesives compared to 5% HMF-containing resins.

Table 4 shows that fructose-HMF(5%)-HMDA has a higher E_A than fructose-HMDA, whereas the E_A of fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT is lower than fructose-BHT. These trends are in accordance with the tensile shear strength in Fig. 4. The increased reactivity of fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT can be seen in the significant gain in tensile shear strength compared to fructose-BHT.

E_A is significantly higher at the initial stages of curing than at the gel point. When E_A does not change with the degree of conversion, the overall reaction mechanism follows a single-step process [30]. This is clearly not the case for the curing process of the studied carbohydrate-amine adhesives, which rather is a kinetically complex process with multiple steps.

In general, a drop in E_A could be due to the formation of highly

Fig. 5. Viscosity as a function of curing time for HMDA-based resins (top left) and BHT-based resins (top right) measured at isothermal conditions of 85 °C with an angular frequency of 10 rad/s and an initial strain of 2%. Symbols are experimental values; lines are from a calculated exponential fit. Arrhenius plot of the viscosity kinetic constant as a function of 1/T for HMDA-based adhesives (bottom left) and BHT-based adhesives (bottom right).

Fig. 6. Arrhenius plot at the gel point of fructose-HMDA (left) and fructose-BHT resins (right) with 5% and 50% HMF contents, based on multiwave experiments at 85 °C, 90 °C and 95 °C.

reactive species at the early stages of curing that need less activation energy for the follow-up reactions. Another plausible explanation would be that certain reactions only take place at the initial stages of curing. As the detailed reaction mechanism of the carbohydrate-amine adhesives is unknown, all possible explanations remain rather speculative at this point and offer ample opportunities for future research.

3.5. Rheokinetics based on isoconversional method

Isoconversional methods have been used for analyzing the curing kinetics of adhesives, such as urea-formaldehyde resins, epoxy/polyfurfuryl alcohol adhesives [47], kraft-lignin phenol-formaldehyde resins [48] or melamine-formaldehyde [49]. More recently, Sangregorio et al. [29] studied the kinetics of crosslinking of humins, which form as byproducts in HMF synthesis. They [29] calculated the activation energy based on isoconversional methods from non-isothermal methods obtained via rheology measurements and demonstrated a good agreement with the kinetic data obtained from isothermal DSC measurements as well as isothermal rheological measurements. Isoconversional methods lead to apparent activation parameters, which depend on the extent of conversion. These parameters can contribute to a deeper understanding of the kinetically complex curing process of carbohydrate-amine adhesives as previous results have already indicated a significant variation of E_A with increasing conversion (Table 4). Correct conversion modelling is an important aspect when using isoconversional methods for the study of rheokinetics. The main advantage of isoconversional methods is that they enable modelling of processes without a mechanistic interpretation and consequently avoid making errors connected with the selection of a reaction model. This advantage also becomes a limiting factor, when isoconversional methods are applied to rheological data. The curing reaction mechanism of the herein studied adhesives was not investigated yet, consequently the degree of conversion has to be determined from the rheological data. In case of the studied adhesives, the material response becomes frequency-independent after the gel point. This makes the calculation of the extent of conversion based on the loss modulus (8) valid from the gel point onward. Before the gel point, the moduli have a frequency dependent behavior. As can be seen in 8 (right plot), the moduli reach the same plateau values, both at the beginning and end of the reaction, when measured at the same frequency with different heating rates.

In order to investigate the effect of the frequency-dependent response at the beginning of the reaction, the degree of conversion was also calculated from isothermal multiwave experiments. It was found that the standard deviation (SD) of α is very small, $SD(\alpha) < 1\%$ (see Supporting Information, Table 4). When the frequency-dependency is not considered and (8) is applied to the non-isothermal measurements,

the gel point is at a critical degree of conversion of 2% ($\alpha_{SG} = 2\% \pm 1\%$) for fructose-BHT (see Fig. 7). α_{gel} is calculated based on the loss modulus in the gel point according to (8). Typically, the conversion at the gel point depends strongly on the functionality of the reaction system and high functionalities give low conversion at the gel point [50].

Taking the standard deviation into account, the validity of α_{SG} must be questioned critically. It can be deduced that the gel point occurs already at small conversions. Summarizing, it can be stated that the gel point occurs already at very low conversions, the standard deviation of α calculated from measurements with different frequencies is small and other rheokinetic methods were previously applied to study the curing reaction at the initial stages before the gel point from isothermal measurements. The application of isoconversional methods using (6) for the studied adhesives is reasonable taking the previous considerations into account.

The results from isothermal measurements showed that the curing of fructose-BHT is faster than fructose-HMDA (Table 4). The apparent activation energy as function of conversion was further analyzed for the most promising adhesives fructose-BHT and fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT. As can be seen in Fig. 8, three main steps can be identified in the course of the apparent activation energy of fructose-BHT adhesives. At small conversions, $\alpha < 4\%$, a sharp decrease of E_A from 94.5 kJ/mol to 57.6 kJ/mol can be observed. The second step is characterized by a linear range from $\alpha = \sim 9\% \sim 30\%$ with an E_A of 60.7 kJ/mol. This almost constant value of the apparent activation energy can be associated with a single step mechanism that determines the overall reaction or parallel processes with constant rate ratios in this range. At conversion of $\alpha > 45\%$, E_A increases significantly. At this point, we assume that the mobility of the molecules was reduced in the curing process leading to a sharp increase of apparent activation energy caused by the increased steric hindrance and decreased mobility as a consequence of the increasing molecular weight. The data for calculating the apparent activation energy of fructose-BHT adhesives and fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT can be found in the Supporting Information.

The course of the apparent activation energy changes drastically when small amounts of HMF (5%) are added. Only two main regions can be identified, a sharp decrease at low conversions ($\alpha < 4\%$) and a linear region for conversion from 9% to full curing (100%). The apparent activation energy of the linear region of fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT is only 28.4 kJ/mol. The apparent activation energy of fructose-BHT resins decreases drastically when HMF is added. This trend was already observed in the activation energy calculated from isothermal measurements in the gel point. These results show that already the addition of small amounts of HMF increases the overall reactivity of fructose-BHT adhesives.

Fig. 7. Degree of conversion (left) as well as G' and G'' (right) as function of temperature at different heating rates exemplary for non-isothermal curing of fructose-BHT.

Fig. 8. Comparison of the apparent activation energy of fructose-BHT adhesives and fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT.

4. Conclusion

The rheological behavior of fructose-(HMF)-amine adhesives was analyzed by performing isothermal, time-sweep experiments together with temperature-sweeps in the linear viscoelastic regime. Four aspects of the curing reaction of these systems were analyzed: (i) rheological characterization of the prepolymer, (ii) initial stages of curing, (iii) the sol-gel transition and (iv) rheokinetic analysis.

Several different amines were screened, varying in chain length and number of functional groups. Chemorheological analysis showed that the characteristic temperatures (T_{CR} , T_{SG}) of fructose-HMDA and fructose-BHT are well within the processing window of wood adhesives, $T < 120$ °C. Neglectable differences in the characteristic temperatures (< 5 °C) were found when HMF is added to those adhesives. A shift to temperatures higher than suitable for the application in wood materials, as reported for other HMF-containing adhesives [2], was not observed in carbohydrate-(HMF)-amine adhesives.

In order to clarify whether the addition of HMF has a significant influence on the curing of carbohydrate-amine adhesives, prepolymers with similar molecular weight were synthesized. The initial assumption

that HMF acts as an additional reactive compound in the prepolymer synthesis was reasonable as the synthesis time of HMF-containing prepolymers was reduced by 2/5 compared to the fructose-amine adhesives in order to obtain similar M_w . HMF-containing prepolymers did not show an increased cure speed in terms of the gel time, but it has to be noted that the gel point corresponds to $< 2\%$ conversion. The crosslink density of the adhesive network is increased when 5% HMF are added in the prepolymer synthesis.

It was found that high amounts of HMF in the adhesive (50% based on fructose content) did not dramatically increase the tensile shear strength compared to adhesives with 5% HMF. As the role of HMF in the reaction mechanism is still unknown, this certainly opens up another topic for future research. The large difference in the HMF content, 5% and 50% respectively, were chosen to see whether positive or negative trends are more pronounced at higher HMF contents. It was found, that already the addition of 5% HMF to carbohydrate-amine adhesives has a positive effect on the adhesive properties such as tensile shear strength. This was underlined by the results from the rheokinetic analysis.

Fructose-HMF(5%)-BHT has a lower activation energy with only 28.4 kJ/mol at 20% conversion compared to fructose-BHT with 60.7 kJ/mol at 20% conversion. In addition, the crosslink density and tensile shear strength increases when 5% HMF are added in the adhesive synthesis.

The presented results provide first insights into the curing behavior of carbohydrate-amine adhesives and highlight the potential of HMF as key reactant in adhesive systems.

Associate content

Supporting Information. Temperature-sweeps of fructose-amine adhesives, characteristic temperatures, exponential and linear fits of viscosity curve, data used for calculation of activation energy according to the isoconversional method. This material is available free of charge via the Internet at <http://pubs.acs.org>.

Author contributions

The manuscript was written through contributions of all authors. All authors have given approval to the final version of the manuscript.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Catherine Thoma: Conceptualization, Methodology, Formal

analysis, Writing – original draft. **Pia Solt-Rindler**: Conceptualization, Writing – review & editing. **Wilfried Sailer-Kronlachner**: Writing – review & editing. **Thomas Rosenau**: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Antje Potthast**: Supervision, Writing – review & editing. **Johannes Konnerth**: Supervision, Resources, Writing – review & editing. **Alessandro Pellis**: Resources, Data curation. **Hendrikus W.G. van Herwijnen**: Conceptualization, Resources, Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial

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Abbreviations

BHT	Bis(hexamethylenetriamine)
c	Polymer concentration at equilibrium [–]
CR	Curing reaction
DMSO	Dimethyl sulfoxide
E_A	Activation energy [kJ/mol]
f	Final
F	Filler
G'	Storage modulus [Pa]
G''	Loss modulus [Pa]
HMDA	Hexamethylenediamine
HMF	5-Hydroxymethylfurfural
i	Initial
K	Viscosity kinetic constant [1/s]
m_0	Initial adhesive mass [g]
m_∞	Adhesive mass at equilibrium swelling [g]
M_n	number average molecular weight [Da]
M_w	weight average molecular weight [Da]
M_c	molecular weight per elastically effective network chain [g/mol]
P	Pressure [Pa]
PDI	Polydispersity index [–]
SG	Sol-gel transition
T	Temperature [K]
t_{gel}	Time at gel point [s]
UF	Urea-formaldehyde adhesive
α	Degree of curing [–]
β	Heating rate [K/min]
γ	Shear rate [1/s]
ρ_P	Polymer density [g/cm ³]
ρ_S	Solvent density [g/cm ³]
ν_E	Crosslink density [mol/m ³]
X	Polymer-solvent interaction parameter [–]

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